

Replication Instructions

Dataset:

input\docs\applist_21082024.csv

Expected size (install packages):

108 GB

Instrumate command line (usage):

Modes of operation: install_from_gp, download_device_apps, analyze, instrumate (to instrument), healthcheck and create databases.

```
options:
-h, --help                show this help message and exit
-m MODE                    Mode of operation. One of: install_from_gp, download_device_apps, analyze, instrumate, healthcheck, create_d
atabase
-d DEVICE_SERIAL          The serial number of target device (use `adb devices` to find)
-a APK_PATH                The file path to target APK
-A APK_DIR                 The dir with APKs
-AS APK_DIR_STRUCTURED    The dir with APKs - Structured dir (instrumented or analyzed)
-f APP_PKG                 The app package ID
-F APP_PKGS                Comma separated list of packages or a file with the list of packages
-o OUTPUT_DIR              output directory
-variant_makers VARIANT_MAKERS
                           List of variant makers
-static_analyzers STATIC_ANALYZERS
                           List of static analyzers
-variant_specs VARIANT_SPECS
                           List of static analyzers
-cfg_dir CONFIG_DIR        Input configuration
-tmp_dir TMP_DIR           Tmp dir. Default is .\tmp
-tools_dir TOOLS_DIR       Tools dir. Default is .\tools
-unfinished_mode UNFINISHED_MODE
                           Any mode that did not finish install_from_gp, download_device_apps, analyze, instrumate, healthcheck, create
database
--debug                    Run in debug mode (dump debug messages).
--force                     Destroy existing files
--all-devices-on-pool      Use all active devices on pool
-emulator_restore_snapshot EMULATOR_RESTORE_SNAPSHOT
                           Restore point to the emulator. Default is None.
-health_check_extra_attempts HEALTH_CHECK_EXTRA_ATTEMPTS
                           Attempts extra N times failed apps before quitting. Default is 2 extra attempts.
-health_check_attempts_per_app HEALTH_CHECK_ATTEMPTS_PER_APP
                           Attempts per app. Useful for non stable AVD environments.
--reboot-device-on-pool-release
                           Reboot device before using (before released by the pool)
--skip_originals           Skip original apps from health checking
--recycle_emulator_with_kill
                           When the device is returned to the pool it is killed. The system should restart it and the pool will wait fo
r it to be available.
--hc_capture_failed_apps   During health check, capture logcat and view state from failed apps
--continue                 Keep existing files and continue previous analysis
```

General instructions

1. Obtain apps from the google play, using the emulator
2. Build the baseline using health check mode (mode healthcheck)
3. Create variants (mode instrumate)
4. Verify variants (mode healthcheck)
5. Compare (using bash scripts inside src/pymate/analysis)

Estimated execution time

Hardware: Workstation z820 with 2 Intel Xeon E5-2687w v2 3.4 GHz 512 GB RAM

1. Original apps: 2 weeks to execute
2. Signature: 1 day to build – 2 Weeks to execute
3. Manifest: 3 days to build – 2 weeks to execute
4. Resources: 3 days to build – 2 weeks to execute
5. G4 - Instrumentation: 1 week to build (per instrumentation strategy) / 2 weeks to execute